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EQ AND IQ: THE PERFECT COMBINATION

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The days when people were evaluated based on their degrees and the number of medals, titles, and accolades they wore on their person are long gone. Then, they are evaluated based on how well they can fit into a "one size fits all" group. But standards also evolve along with people. Metamorphosis occurs in all living things, including those who are still and breathing. Over time, nothing remains constant.

People's ability and capacity to survive in the workplace are now assessed differently. Age has brought about a new norm, a criterion that rejects the outdated, constrictive, and limited notion of humanity at work. The interpersonal skills that are often referred to as "emotional competencies" are even more important in the workplace than intellectual ability. It's not enough for people to be intelligent, well-educated, and knowledgeable in a certain profession; they also need to be capable at managing themselves and other people.

People have had to learn this truth the hard way. Someone who graduated with honors from a prestigious or top-tier university would believe that everything was perfect for him because the distinction had already given him an advantage over others. As one immerses himself in the world of work, he or she will quickly come to the realization that intelligence is not everything; what matters most is that they have a positive and productive working connection with their coworkers.

According to research, intelligence alone is insufficient. Not everyone in the world is happy and successful, even the most intelligent ones. Surprisingly, they frequently aren't the ones who bring about major international changes. Emotional quotient (EQ) is a topic of rising discussion among psychologists and neuroscientists. They contend that EQ is a must for successfully utilizing IQ. People with high EQs are able to properly manage their own emotions while also interacting and relating to others. Human relations afterwards developed.

As Daniel Goleman demonstrated convincingly and correctly than two decades ago, Emotional Intelligence (EQ) is more important to leadership effectiveness and success than IQ. The majority of attempts, meanwhile, have only led to momentary advances. The lack of a deeper, core intellect—which comes before having a high EQ—is the root of the problem. In my Stanford University lectures, I use the term Positive Intelligence (PQ) to describe this. Without a solid PQ basis, many of our attempts to better ourselves end in failure because of self-sabotage.

Personal traits like initiative, empathy, adaptability, persuasion, flexibility, cooperation, teamwork skills in resolving conflict, creativity in handling setbacks and obstacles, and self-motivation to learn, grow, and collaborate with others are all examples of personal qualities.

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Additionally, the word "EQ" is used to describe additional elements that may promote good relationships and the capacity to react correctly and favorably to daily challenges. It involves identifying feelings and controlling them. Without a tangible manifestation, emotions are simply collections of thoughts. In order to talk about emotions, we first need to understand them, develop a language for them, and then be able to express them. EQ deals with knowing who we are, how we relate to others, and how other people see us. Additionally, EQ enables us to build richer, more rewarding connections by assisting us in comprehending how others are feeling. All of this is necessary if we want to be able to manage conflicts as they emerge and work cooperatively and jointly in daily situations.

The ability to interact with others is significantly more vital than mental faculties. In the society we live in, having a wide range of interpersonal skills is quite valuable. No man is an island, after all. Isn't it true that people exist for others, serving as their primary reason for existing? People must look beyond what is immediately apparent, particularly in the workplace, in business, and in trade.

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